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A RED-LETTER DAY IN THE ANNALS OF CARRIGFADDA

Church Building, Nationalism and the Pull of Rome

Finola Finlay

This paper looks at some of the social and religious movements of the opening decades of the twentieth century through the lens of one small West Cork church. A close reading of the building and a three-light stained glass window within it reveals clear evidence of the political orientation of those who commissioned it. Analysis of the rhetoric used in the dedication ceremonies of churches of this era underscores how church-building could be equated with Irish nationalism while at the same time emphasising the Rome-centric nature of Irish Catholicism. It is also the story of two Clonakilty men, uncle and nephew, who left their mark on West Cork.

St Peter's Roman Catholic church in Carrigfadda, in the present Diocese of Cork and Ross and the parish of Rosscarbery and Lisavaird, was built in 1907–08 by Fr Peter Hill (Fig 1).¹ Fifteen years after Fr Hill died in 1912, his nephew, referred to throughout this paper as Monsignor (Msgr) Peter Hill to distinguish him from his uncle, installed a three-light stained glass window in the church chancel, in part to memorialise his uncle and namesake. The window depicts St Peter, flanked by St Brigid and St Patrick. The architecture of the church, its

Fig 1: St Peter's Church, Carrigfadda (photo: author).

construction during a period of rural poverty and emigration, and the design of the stained glass window capture the zeitgeist of Irish Catholicism in the opening decades of the twentieth century. This paper explores what a simple country church like that in Carrigfadda can tell us about the cultural and historical context in which it was established.

The church that Fr Hill built is a simple 'barn style' building but with clear indications of the influence of the neo-Romanesque style that was becoming popular with Catholic clergy at the time. The windows are round-headed as is the main door which features surrounding chevrons. The only other external decorative features are the cut stone staggered quoins and window surrounds. The church merely hints at its Romanesque aspirations, being a modest country church, as befitted its situation and no doubt its budget. Inside, the church is quite plain, though with the usual ornamentations, including the stained glass.

In the early twentieth century, Romanesque-inspired architecture was favoured as an expression of the national identity of the Irish Church. Its motivation was the belief that the twelfth-century Hiberno-Romanesque style, as seen in Cormac's Chapel on the Rock of Cashel, for example, was

a truly indigenous form of church-building, harking back to the great age of Irish saints and scholars. Richard Hurley, one of Ireland's most prestigious modern architects and an historian of modern Irish church architecture, gives his interpretation of this mindset:

... the [re-]emergence of Hiberno-Romanesque architecture was associated with the rise of Irish nationalism and the eventual road to independence. In the minds of some in the Catholic Church particularly, it was believed that a church building would not be true unless its inspiration and its design was sincerely Irish and recalled much that was most distinctive and suggestive in the best age of Irish ecclesiastical art.²

The Rev. Sir John R. O'Connell, the Dublin solicitor and later priest, was the executor of the bequest of Isabella Honan. He used the bequest to fund the building of a hostel and chapel at University College Cork.³ Writing in 1916 about the Honan Chapel, considered the gem of twentieth-century Hiberno-Romanesque architecture, O'Connell lays out the basis for a distinctly Irish form of church architecture:

... for Irishmen there is another law which ought to mould and fashion church buildings in this country, viz., that our churches should be freed from foreign influences, and that they should be faithful to those early Celtic forms to be found in so many places in this country, which for want of a better term are known as Hiberno-Romanesque ... its claim is based on grounds stronger than those of architectural symmetry and beauty. It brings us back to the early ages of the faith in Ireland. It reminds us of the labours and the works of the Saints who brought the faith to our people, and who confirmed them in it.⁴

Ironically, this was somewhat erroneous, since the Romanesque style was pan-European rather than specifically Irish. Additionally, it post-dated by centuries the perceived 'Golden Age' of the early Irish Church. Nevertheless, it offered a nationalistic alternative to classical and Gothic architecture.

Another local example of a Romanesque-influenced building is the 1932 Sacred Heart Church at Drinagh, only 6km to the northwest of Carrigfadda,

although the style of Drinagh is much more exuberantly expressed, with greater external and internal detail.⁵ However, the high point of neo-Romanesque architecture in West Cork is represented by another church in the Diocese of Ross, masterminded by Msgr Peter Hill: the Church of the Nativity of the Blessed Virgin Mary, whose construction was started in 1907 but was not dedicated until 1912. Dominating the town of Timoleague, that church features an engaged round tower, a Romanesque doorway with four orders supported by red marble pillars, and extensive internal decoration.⁶ In contrast, the Carrigfadda church is as plain as it is possible to be while still referencing a Romanesque style.

At the same time as the church was constructed, Fr Hill built Carrigfadda House for the curate. An ample building, its design echoes that of the church in its round-headed doorway and stone detailing. Now a private residence, it was of a type known as a ‘split’ house – one which provided for separate quarters for a housekeeper – and was very fine, with marble fireplaces and large and commodious rooms (Fig 2).

Fig 2: Carrigfadda House, built in c.1907 by Fr Hill for the priest assigned to Carrigfadda (photo: author).

Fr Hill came from a prosperous Clonakilty family and this residence may have reflected his own expectations. The Hills of Clonakilty had numerous businesses, particularly related to milling and agricultural supplies.⁷ The young Peter was sent to St Patrick's College, Carlow, at that time one of the few options available in Ireland for the education of young Catholic men whose parents could afford it. After that, he received his theological training in the Irish College in Paris, eventually being ordained in February 1864 in St Anne's Church (no longer extant) on Western Road in Clonakilty.⁸ Fr Hill was posted to curacies in various parishes around West Cork, including Skibbereen where he carried out improvements to the pro-cathedral, and to Lisavaird where he undertook a building programme to renovate the ageing church built c.1820. He eventually became parish priest of Rosscarbery from 1887 to 1912.⁹ His responsibilities included St Fachtna's Church in Rosscarbery, the Sacred Heart Church in Lisavaird and later St Peter's Church in Carrigfadda, as well as the various schools in the parish and the convent in Rosscarbery. In 1893 he gifted a stained glass window to the Rosscarbery church (Fig 3). Located

Fig 3: West window in St Fachtna's Church, Rosscarbery, gifted by Fr Hill in 1893 (photo: author).

above the west door and partly hidden by the balcony, the window consists of the Sacred Heart flanked by Patrick and Brigid, and bears the words 'Pray for the Very Rev Peter Hill, PP VF, 1893'.¹⁰ There is no maker's mark on this window and it is impossible to identify what studio it is from.

Fr Hill was an active and energetic clergyman, one of the band that Richard Butler calls 'church-building priests',¹¹ introducing the Mercy Sisters to Rosscarbery (their fine convent dominates the landscape of the Rosscarbery Lagoon to this day) and obviously esteemed by his colleagues, who elected him vicar capitular of the diocese. It was he, in his capacity as parish priest of Rosscarbery, who baptised Michael Collins in 1890.¹²

The 1901 census shows a population of nearly 700, almost entirely Catholic, in the Cahermore District Electoral Division, in which Carrigfadda is located.¹³ As the crow flies, the closest churches to Carrigfadda, which is situated in a rural landscape, were in Drinagh,¹⁴ in the parish of Drimoleague, 6km to the northwest and in Rosscarbery, 7km to the southeast. This meant that the large Catholic population in the Carrigfadda area had to travel a significant distance to attend Mass. Clearly this area was in need of a church of its own, and Fr Hill set about building that church, which would be attached to the parish of Rosscarbery. His name and that of Rev. Denis Kelly, Bishop of Ross, are engraved on the 1907 foundation stone (Fig 4). The church was consecrated and opened the following year, 1908.

Fig 4: Foundation stone at Carrigfadda church, dating to 1907 (photo: author).

The estimate for the cost of the church was £2,000 and by 1906 £450 had been raised.¹⁵ We are indebted to Con O'Callaghan¹⁶ for an account of how the location for the church was selected:

The first [problem] was that the annual dues were not large enough to support an extra priest. The second was where this man would be placed. With the help of Bishop Kelly, the parish priest Rev P Hill PP made the case to Rome. They were able to show that the neighbouring parish of Kilmacabea had more income than was needed to support its clergy. So in typical fashion of that time, it was decided to transfer 10 townlands from Kilmacabea to Rosscarbery ... At that time many people expected the chapel would be built in the village of Reenascreena, but Rev P Hill PP had a different view. He did not want it near a public house, and so the chapel was built in a central place, but a very isolated spot ... The land for the Church was acquired from the McCarthy and O'Sullivan families of Carrigfadda ... The builders were the O'Donovan's (Rinnee) of Ross, noted contractors at that time.¹⁷

O'Callaghan's account tells us that the appropriation of townlands from one parish to another did cause some lingering resentment. We have no information on whether the land was donated free of charge or how the rest of the money was raised to build the church, although the stained glass window dedicated to Fr Hill's memory says that he 'Built this Church by Parish Exiles and Home Friends'. It was normal at the time for large fundraising efforts to be conducted for new churches and these efforts often took the form of soliciting donations from people who were native to the place but who had emigrated. The era of major church-building in Ireland had commenced in the period after Catholic Emancipation in 1829, stalled during and immediately after the Famine, then reached its high point in the 1860s to the 1930s, continuing unabated into the 1960s. Butler's analysis of the building of the Church of Mary Immaculate in Dromore (25km west of Carrigfadda) in the 1950s charts many of the same themes that this essay explores, despite the church being built nearly half a century later.¹⁸

Church-building itself was equated with nationalistic fervour – a statement of strength and independence after centuries of the suppression of Catholicism and the impoverishment of its adherents. The following landscape analysis of churches by Martin Maguire starts off within the English context before contrasting this with the situation in Ireland:

As icons of history and cultural identity churches are richly symbolic and emotional sites of legitimation in the landscape ... A slender steeple or a solid bell-tower seen across field and woodland or over city and town evokes reflections on transience, endurance and community. They are icons of time and memory and, at the same time, statements of both a local and a national identity ... For communities they are the focus of deeply territorial instincts of place and memory. Churches offer a stable point in a changing landscape that symbolises ageless values ... For the English visitor used to reading churches as symbols of continuity the Irish landscape is strange because, although laden with similar signs of symbolic intent inscribing signs of meaning and structure on the landscape, it resists familiar readings. In an Irish landscape churches have different meanings ... Churches in the Irish landscape are not part of a landscape of shared belief, nor are they symbols of continuity. Rather are they part of a landscape of power and conflict, dissonant symbols of resistance and colonisation. For centuries the meaning of this landscape has been contested in a struggle for ownership and legitimation ... churches are also ways of staking claims to the landscape and are political statements about the ownership of space and place.¹⁹

Recent scholarly work has analysed the social and historical context and symbolism surrounding the building of new churches in the increasingly nationalistic society of nineteenth- and early twentieth-century Ireland. Niamh NicGhabhann has described the ritualised foundation-stone ceremonies that attended the building of new Catholic churches as ‘highly symbolic and significant in terms of the forging of shared narratives within the community itself’.²⁰ She reminds us that all such ceremonies took place

within the context of a strict form of ultramontane Catholicism which looked to Rome as the primary authority in all matters. NicGhabhann says that,

... exploration of the foundation stone ceremonies reveals the extent to which fund-raising campaigns were mobilised throughout the community, building on narratives of national political resurgence, the occupation of land and perceived triumph over historical adversity. In his sermon during the foundation stone ceremony for the new church at Cloughjordan, Co. Tipperary, in 1898, for example, Dr Denis Kelly, Bishop of Ross, described the new building as ‘a development of practical Catholic emancipation’, encouraging the congregation to see the church as part of past political victories and ongoing political change, as much as a place of spiritual worship and reflection. This rhetoric echoes the ideologies of the Land War of 1879 to 1903, described by Cormac Ó Gráda as involving ‘a return of the land to people who saw themselves as descendants of those who had lost their lands in the bloody Tudor, Cromwellian, and Williamite confiscations of the sixteenth and seventeenth centuries’, despite the many contradictions and complications within that narrative.²¹

It was this same Bishop Kelly that presided over the foundation-stone ceremony at Carrigfadda. While his speech was not reported in full in the *Skibbereen Eagle*, we can have little doubt that it was similar in tone to the one he delivered in Cloughjordan, and also similar to that delivered by Dr Michael Fogarty, Bishop of Killaloe, when the magnificent church at Timoleague, built through the exertions of Fr Hill’s nephew, Msgr Peter Hill, was dedicated in 1912.²² (It seems that the bishops were doing a *quid pro quo* of opening ceremonies, since Cloughjordan is in the Diocese of Killaloe.) Bishop Fogarty was a noted nationalist and orator who ‘involved himself closely in the social and political challenges facing Ireland’.²³ Fogarty’s speech is remarkable to the modern ear as much for its nuance-free and emotive evocation of the centuries of Irish oppression as for the note of sectarianism that emanated from deep and long-held resentments, but it seems to have been fairly typical of the speeches given by churchmen

on such occasions and is worth quoting at length to provide an instance of what the congregation were listening to.

‘For many years’, said Bishop Fogarty, ‘the faithful of Timoleague worshipped God in one of the poorest of churches ... The Church in Ireland had passed out of its long night of persecution: she had entered on the bright dawn of freedom with renewed vigour, and her faithful sons and daughters strove to reconstruct her temples ...’. He went on to castigate those who criticise the expenditure of money on churches,

as if they begrudged to the service of the Most High a shilling of that wealth they squander so lavishly in the service of man. For it is to be observed that the people who speak this – and I am happy to say that they are not Catholics – but if they worship at all for the most part worship in churches which they never built, but which they plundered by violence from others who built them – have neither scruple nor objection to that limitless expenditure which we every day witness in erecting public buildings, courts of justice, banks, Royal palaces, and private dwellings, some of which ... have cost more money than would build all the churches in Connacht. But let the poor Irish man spend a shilling in honour of that God whom he adores ... let a new window be painted, and organ erected, and we are told at once that this is money misapplied, that it shocks the economic sense, that it had been better spent in starting industries or given to the poor.

He continued,

Poor plundered Ireland. What a history has been hers. Nowhere else in the world has the faith of the people passed through so many ordeals of persecution without being conquered. Of temptation without being shaken, of scandal without being corrupted. And, therefore, much as I admire this splendid building and rejoice with you in its consecration, it is not, I confess, the beauty of its architecture, nor the solidity of its structure, nor the amplitude of its dimensions that move me now, but the thought of what it represents and stands for, the triumph of our long persecuted faith. Your Catholic ancestors lie buried for

many generations around the walls of the old monastery yonder,²⁴ now roofless and in ruins. They passed out of life, those brave soldiers of the faith, apparently defeated in their long and direful struggle for God and country; and when they died everything seemed lost to Ireland – land, freedom and religion. But the flag for which they fought was not buried; nor was the spirit which spread it fearlessly to the breeze, despite all opposition, extinguished in the land. The blood which they shared as martyrs carried in it the seeds of ultimate triumph, and your noble new church, now built and consecrated in an atmosphere of freedom, is the fruit, as it is also a monument of the illustrious and lasting victory won for Catholic Ireland by these, our faithful forefathers. Their race and blood have passed through many vicissitudes of fortune since the dark and disastrous night of Kinsale; they have suffered many a wrong and many humiliations in the intervening centuries, and have undergone many great and sorrowful changes ...

Referring to the fundraising needed to build a church like this, by voluntary contribution and without any form of state aid, he stated,

... though this system may sometimes press hard upon us, and though our richly endowed Protestant neighbours may sneer at our sometimes humble efforts, I regard it not only as a tribute to the intensity of our faith, but as a merciful dispensation of Providence for the preservation of the holy faith in the hearts of our people ... the result of this system is that our priests and churches belong to the people themselves – that is the Irish priest as a rule is sprung from the people amongst whom he ministers. He is one of themselves, bone of their bone and flesh of their flesh. His heart and theirs keep perfect time and empathy. He is no foreigner, no outsider, no distant Aristocrat who disdains their humble lives, or chills them with his lofty airs. As a rule he comes of a family, oftentimes poor enough, but of an old stock long rooted in the soil and of decent and honourable principle ... he loves his people with the double love of a priest and a brother, and they love and respect him as a true friend and spiritual father.

Fr Hill seems indeed to have been one of those ‘bone of our bone’ priests. There are charming accounts of the affection in which he was held by his fellow clergy and by his parishioners. The celebrations attendant on his silver jubilee were reported in the *Skibbereen Eagle* in 1889, at which occasion he was presented with a portrait of himself and (very popular at the time) an illuminated address, toasts were offered to Pope Leo XIII and to ‘Ireland a Nation’, and several speeches were delivered of a highly nationalistic nature.²⁵ While the portrait itself cannot be traced there is a worn photograph of it in a cabinet in the Carrigfadda church. It shows a clean-shaven and thoughtful man, one elbow on a pile of books and the other hand wound around a rosary (Fig 5).

Fr Hill died in 1912 on 14 August²⁶ and as reported by the *Cork Examiner* by the time his funeral cortege reached Rosscarbery, ‘it assumed immense proportions and everywhere was manifested genuine respect and regret

Fig 5: Very old and worn photograph, in Carrigfadda Church, of the portrait of Fr Hill presented to him on the occasion of his silver jubilee in 1889.

amply testifying to ... how he had enshrined himself in the hearts of his people'.²⁷ A tribute to his memory appearing in the *Skibbereen Eagle* later that month referred to how he had thrown himself 'heart and soul into the [Land] movement on behalf of the tenant farmers and ... was instrumental in effecting many settlements and owing to his great influence had two evicted tenants reinstated'.²⁸ There is a memorial tablet to him inside the porch of the Rosscarbery church – a finely executed brass plaque written in Latin but using Irish script, embellished with capital letters and borders of interlacing (Fig 6).

Fig 6: Memorial plaque to Fr Peter Hill in St Fachtna's Church, Rosscarbery (photo: author).

To the surprise of many, his nephew, Msgr Peter Hill, was appointed parish priest of Rosscarbery the very day after the dedication of the Timoleague church at which Bishop Fogarty had delivered his fiery oration. Msgr Hill stayed in Rosscarbery until 1921, when he was transferred to Clonakilty where he was promoted to monsignor and served until his death in 1948. Like his uncle, Fr Hill, he was of a nationalistic cast of mind and a champion of the Irish language. As can be appreciated from the design of the Timoleague church and the patriotic tenor of the Hills in general, Msgr Hill espoused the artistic expressions of nationalism then in favour: Hiberno-Romanesque in architecture and the ‘Celtic Revival’ motifs in art, such as interlace and spiral decoration, as well as Gaelic script, all of which were inspired by early medieval works of art.²⁹ It may well have been he who ordered and dictated the design of the brass memorial plaque (Fig. 6).

Msgr Hill turned to Watsons of Youghal when the time came to order the Carrigfadda window. Up to the turn of the century most stained glass had been imported. Caroline McGee, in her essay on the Clongowes Wood College Chapel, points out that ‘Foreign firms traded successfully until the turn of the century, when the merits of imported church furniture began to be reassessed in the light of hardening cultural nationalist opinion’.³⁰ Watsons was one of the many new businesses established to respond to the demand for Irish-made church furnishings. Set up originally as an Irish branch of the British firm Cox, Sons, Buckley and Co., one of its employees, James Watson ‘bought out the Youghal branch in the mid 1890s and his descendants made stained glass windows there until 2012’.³¹ Watsons was a prolific provider of stained glass throughout Ireland and especially Munster. What may have made them particularly attractive to Msgr Hill was that they specialised in Celtic Revival decoration.³²

This element of the windows – the extensive and intricate Revivalist interlacing – provides an insight into the artistic predilections of Irish Catholic clergy at this time.³³ The choice of figures, however, illuminates the interplay between an ultramontane orientation to Rome and a desire for a truly Irish representation of saintly models.

Paul Cullen had been appointed Catholic archbishop of Armagh by Pius IX in 1850 with the specific task of aligning the Church in Ireland with mainstream

European Catholicism. By the turn of the century this objective had been thoroughly met and Ireland was well provided with new churches and with a constant supply of priests and nuns from the new seminaries and convents. Ultramontane Catholicism placed papal authority as central to the conduct of the Church and its members. In part, nineteenth-century ultramontanistism was a reaction to the horrors of the French Revolution but also to Bismarck's interpretation of nationalism, which imposed state supervision on church activities. Cullen was an arch-Romanist. In his engaging study, *Ireland Since 1800: conflict and conformity*, K. T. Hoppen says, 'Cullen, one of the towering figures of modern Irish history, had spent virtually all his earlier career in Rome where he had been inoculated against liberalism in its continental form'.³⁴

Cullen ushered in what Emmet Larkin termed the 'devotional revolution'. In his seminal essay on this form of Irish Catholicism, Larkin says, 'the devotional revolution and its general and particular causes are crucial to understanding the development of Irish Nationalism and the cultural importance of Irish Catholicism in that development'.³⁵

No longer trained in an Irish college in Paris or Rome but graduates of Maynooth, Cullen's new army of priests were more likely to espouse the causes of Irish independence and land reform and to embrace popular perceptions of Irishness in language, arts and literature. A great wave of interest in the origins and development of the Church in Ireland led to many translations from Irish of the various martyrologies and lives of the saints, and adoption and veneration of Irish, and indeed highly localised, saints became a staple of parishes and dioceses.

The east window (Fig. 7) in Carrigfadda church illustrates this duality beautifully: St Peter is central, not only because this is the Church of St Peter but to represent the ever-present authority of Rome, and he is flanked by St Patrick and St Brigid. Rather than the usual gothic canopies, each saint is surrounded by intricate and carefully executed interlace patterns. Although they are finely painted, the figures are generic and undistinguished; it is the Revivalist interlacing that lifts the windows from the ordinary. Vera Ryan's research into Watsons of Youghal has shown how priests would specifically request 'Keltic' decoration³⁶ and Watsons became expert in this form of artwork.

Fig 7: Carrigfadda church east window, produced by Watsons of Youghal in 1927 (photo: author).

Fig 8: Full-size drawing of the figure of St Peter, used in both the Carrigfadda three-light window (1927) and the Rosscarbery five-light window (1929), kept in the Watsons archive in Crawford Art Gallery, Cork (photo: author).

The Watsons archive is now in the Crawford Art Gallery in Cork city. It consists of order books, ledgers, small design drawings, and full-size cartoons and figure drawings.³⁷ Because of the fragility of the cartoons and large drawings, it is only possible to consult a photographic record. However, the full-size drawing for the St Peter figure which featured in the Carrigfadda window is among those photographs (Fig 8),³⁸ as well as one very similar to the St Patrick figure at Carrigfadda. This is not surprising, as these cartoons were used over and over,

and all three saints were popular choices. However, their reuse results in stained glass windows that are unoriginal and this contributes to our failure to even notice stained glass eventually, since so many of the windows look the same.

Although the Watsons collection consists of what was saved from the studios and is hit and miss in terms of years, some order books were saved, including the book for 1927, showing that 'Order 3326 January 1927 was from Rt Rev Mgr Hill for a 3 light window of SS Peter Patrick and Brigid

Receipts 29

1927	LEDER	Total	LEDER Sales	Cash Sales	Dundries	Cash refunded	Cheques Drains
	Brought Forward	1273 11 4	604 10 11	13 6		50 10 -	617 19 11
May 14	Bennetts Iron Foundry	2 2 2					2 2 2
14	John Lyons	35 5 -					5 - -
17	Dr Konaque	2 10 -	2 10 -				
18	Mr Daly	2 18 9	2 18 9				
April 20	Jmt Enam Co. Loan	9 2 2			9 2 2		
April 2	Income tax Fin. Loan	2 5 7					2 5 7
May 18	B. No. 18 Stomas	8 5 -					8 5 -
19	Dean M ^{rs} Merney	18 10 -	18 10 -				
	J. A. Gallard Ret'd	9 - -				9 - -	
20	M. Collins Ret'd	5 - -				5 - -	
20	Dr Murphy P.A.	3 10 -					3 10 -
20	Drawn Selves	10 - -					10 - -
19	From Small Orders	19 - -		19 - -			
21	From Canon Carrigan	15 10 -	15 10 -				
21	Drawn Selves	44 18 4					44 18 4
25	Cheque Telephone Co.	2 3 11					2 3 11
26	Cheque Drawn Selves	5 - -					5 - -
28	From Mgr Hill	282 - -	282 - -				
28	Cash From Small Orders	5 6 -		5 6 -			
28	From Mr Carrigan	17 5 -	17 5 -				
28	Drawn Selves	47 9 -					47 9 -

Fig 9: Watsons of Youghal receipt book from 1927 showing a payment from Msgr Hill for the Carrigfadda window (photo: author).

in St Peter's Church Carrigfadda, Rosscarbery, £284'.³⁹ The receipt book for 1927 also shows a payment from Msgr Hill of £282 on 28 May (Fig 9). A couple of years later, in 1929, the Rosscarbery church ordered the large five-light window that is still in place there, and the same cartoon was used for St Peter. It may seem strange that Msgr Hill would wait fifteen years before ordering a memorial window for his uncle for the Carrigfadda church, but it could be that the opportunity arose for him when two other parties wished to present windows and the cost became a joint venture. While the central panel of St Peter is in memory of Fr Peter Hill, the Brigid window was donated by the parish priest of Ardfield, Fr Kearney, for his parents who lived in Sunny Rock near the church, and the Patrick window by the children of William and Margaret Barrett of Glanbrack, also nearby.

Despite the presence of the Irish saints and the Revivalist decoration – all hallmarks of Irish nationalism – the authority of Rome is emphasised in several ways in both the Peter and Patrick windows. Peter, of course, is equated with Rome, being considered the first pope and holding the keys of heaven, the symbol of papal authority.⁴⁰ To underscore this, the predella (lowest panel of the window) contains St Ambrose's phrase: '*Ubi Petrus Ibi Ecclesia*', usually translated as 'Where Peter is, There is the Church'. The topmost section contains an image of the papal crown (known as the tiara), which often functions on its own as a sort of shorthand for papal authority.

Patrick is shown in his traditional representation as a bishop, holding a crozier and the shamrock. In the predella, surrounded by interlace and triskeles, is the image of a book with the words '*Ut Christiani Ita, Et Romani Sitis*' (Fig 10). This is a more interesting and, more controversial, phrase, which has been translated as 'As you are Christians, be Ye also Children of Rome'. It has been attributed to St Patrick himself, but in fact does not occur in any of his writings,⁴¹ rather it was inserted into the text of Tírechán's *Vita S. Patricii* in the Book of Armagh (folio 9).⁴² Much has been written about the correct translation of this phrase, including the theory that it is an exhortation to Patrick's followers to sing the *Kyrie*, 'as they do in Rome'.⁴³ However, ascribing it to Patrick, and interpreting it as a directive from our patron saint himself to follow the dictates of Rome, has been a useful interpretation for ultramontanists and the phrase is the motto of the Irish college in Rome, of

Fig 10: Predella (lowest panel) of the Patrick window of Carrigfadda church (photo: author).

which Cullen served as the rector for seventeen years before being dispatched to Armagh in 1850.

Writing about the church in Charleville (a much grander building than Carrigfadda), Caroline McGee, in her analysis of the building and its art and furniture, sees that same duality and concludes ‘the Church of the Holy Cross, Charleville, can be seen to express multiple authorities, the prime one being the ideology and authority of the Rome-centric Irish Catholic Church’.⁴⁴ Similarly, in this unassuming little church at Carrigfadda in rural Co. Cork we can discern, by looking closely, some of the great movements of the age for Irish Catholics: nationalism, the Celtic Revival and the pull of Rome.

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Notes

- 1 The title of this essay comes from a report in the *Skibbereen Eagle* of 27 November 1909, upon the occasion of the first Mass said in the new church. At the time the church was built, Cork and Ross had not been amalgamated so Carrigfadda (sometimes spelled ‘Carrigfada’) was then in the Diocese of Ross.
- 2 Hurley, R. 2001. *Irish Church Architecture in the Era of Vatican II*. Dublin, p. 12.
- 3 Hogan, D. 2009. ‘O’Connell, Sir John Robert’, in the Dictionary of Irish Biography, <https://www.dib.ie/biography/oconnell-sir-john-robert-a6564> [accessed 30/09/2021].
- 4 O’Connell, J. R. 1916. *The Honan Hostel Chapel Cork: Some notes on the building and the ideals which inspired it*. Cork, p. 21.
- 5 National Inventory of Architectural Heritage (hereafter NIAH), no. 20912002, <https://www.buildingsofireland.ie/buildings-search/building/20912002/sacred-heart-roman-catholic-church-paddock-drinagh-cork>.
- 6 NIAH, no. 20856003, <https://www.buildingsofireland.ie/buildings-search/building/20856003/church-of-the-nativity-of-our-lady-chapel-hill-timoleague-timoleague-cork>.
- 7 Clonakilty’s library on Kent Street was built as a mill by Thomas Hill and Co. Ltd in the early nineteenth century. The Hills also owned a milling complex on Western Road and the site is now occupied by Clonakilty Food Company.
- 8 For more on this church, which was built in 1800–02 and is no longer extant, see O’Neill, C. 2021. ‘Fr William O’Brien: providing the groundwork for social inclusion in Clonakilty (1798–1815)’. *Clonakilty Historical & Archaeological Journal*, this vol.
- 9 The website of the Diocese of Cork and Ross (<https://corkandross.org>) has a biographical sketch of most priests who have served in the diocese. I have used this helpful site to check details of both the Hill priests, as well some others.
- 10 I am not sure how common it was for priests in general to gift stained glass windows to their church, with a request to pray for them. The large east window in the same church was ‘presented’ by subsequent priests serving there, and Fr Hill’s nephew, Msgr Hill, presented a large window to the church he eventually moved to, the Immaculate Conception in Clonakilty, with the inscription ‘Pray for Rt Rev Monsignor Peter Hill, PP, VO, AD 1937’.
- 11 Butler, R. J. 2020. ‘Building a Catholic church in 1950s Ireland: architecture, rhetoric and

- landscape in Dromore, Co. Cork, 1952–6'. *Rural History* 31, pp. 223–49.
- 12 Forester, M. 2006 (1st publ. 1971). *Michael Collins: The lost leader*. Dublin, p. 3.
- 13 National Archives, Census of Ireland, 1901, available online at <http://www.census.nationalarchives.ie/> [accessed 30/09/2021].
- 14 An older church was then located across the road from the current church built in 1932 (discussed earlier).
- 15 *Southern Star*, 17 Nov. 1906, 'Proposed new church'.
- 16 Con O'Callaghan was the writer of *St. Peter's: The church beneath the hill* but I have been unable to source the original document. I am relying on information contained in the online public profile of John Crowley on the genealogy website, GENi, available at <https://www.geni.com/people/John-Crowley/6000000117769951895> [accessed 30/09/2021].
- 17 Profile John Crowley, GENi.
- 18 Butler, 'Building a Catholic church in 1950s Ireland'.
- 19 Maguire, M. 2004. 'Churches and symbolic power in the Irish landscape'. *Landscapes* 5(2), pp. 91–114.
- 20 NicGhabhann, N. 2019. 'A development of practical Catholic Emancipation': laying the foundations for the Roman Catholic urban landscape, 1850–1900'. *Urban History* 46(1), pp. 44–61, at p. 46.
- 21 NicGhabhann, 'A development of practical Catholic Emancipation', p. 51.
- 22 The speech delivered by Fogarty is quoted in full in the *Skibbereen Eagle*, 14 Sep. 1912. All Bishop Fogarty's quotes are from that article, 'Solemn dedication by his lordship Bishop of Ross/Impressive ceremonies/Eloquent sermon by his lordship the Bishop of Killaloe'.
- 23 Ferriter, D. 2009. 'Fogarty, Michael', in the Dictionary of Irish Biography, <https://www.dib.ie/biography/fogarty-michael-a3307> [accessed 30/09/2021].
- 24 Bishop Fogarty was referring to the ruins of Timoleague Friary, located at the bottom of the hill upon which the new church was built. It was then, and remains, a potent symbol of the dissolution of the monasteries of the sixteenth century.
- 25 *Skibbereen Eagle*, 28 Sep. 1889, 'Silver jubilee'.
- 26 The 14 August is the feast of St Fachtna, patron saint of Rosscarbery and the Diocese of Ross.
- 27 *Cork Examiner*, 16 Aug. 1912, 'Late Rev Peter Hill'.
- 28 *Skibbereen Eagle*, 24 Aug. 1912, under the headline 'Clonakilty Board of Guardians'.
- 29 I use the term 'Celtic Revival' throughout this paper advisedly. While Irish historians and archaeologists no longer subscribe to the theory of an Iron Age invasion of Celts, the term is a familiar one which designates a particular set of artistic styles based on what Victorian antiquarians believed to be an art form dating back to early medieval Ireland, such as that found, for example, in the Book of Kells and high crosses. While any references to the Irish as Celts is no longer supportable, art historians have not yet generally agreed on a term to replace Celtic Revival as a descriptor of this turn-of-the-century nationalistic fascination with this perceived 'indigenous' art form.
- 30 McGee, C. M. 2014/15. 'A reverence peculiarly its own': the boys' chapel at Clongowes Wood College'. *Studies: An Irish Quarterly Review* 103(412), pp. 499–515, at p. 500.
- 31 Ryan, V. 2015. 'Divine light: a century of stained glass'. *Irish Arts Review*, 32(2), pp. 272–75,

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- available online at <https://www.irishartsreview.com/divine-light-a-century-of-stained-glass/> [accessed 30/09/2021].
- 32 Finlay, F. 2019. 'Watsons of Youghal, Revivalist masters', online at <https://roaringwaterjournal.com/2019/10/13/watsons-of-youghal-revivalist-masters-part-1/> and <https://roaringwaterjournal.com/2019/10/19/watsons-of-youghal-revivalist-masters-part-2/> [accessed 30/09/2021].
- 33 For a thorough discussion on the influence of the Celtic Revival style in art, see Sheehy, J. 1980. *The Rediscovery of Ireland's Past: The Celtic Revival 1830-1930*. London.
- 34 Hoppen, K. T. 1989. *Ireland Since 1800: conflict and conformity*. London and New York, p. 143.
- 35 Larkin, E. 1972. 'The devotional revolution in Ireland, 1850-75'. *American Historical Review* 77, pp. 625-52, at p. 650.
- 36 Vera Ryan, pers. comm.
- 37 A stained glass window usually starts with a small design drawing. From this drawing a full-size sketch, called a cartoon, is made of the overall composition of the windows. The cartoon shows the shape of each piece of glass and indicates the chosen colours and various details to be painted on each piece. A full-size drawing is useful for tracing the central figure onto the glass, while the cartoon is used as a guide for cutting and painting the glass and for arranging the pieces between the lead 'comes'.
- 38 This full-size figure of St Peter was used often by Watsons: for example, it occurs in both Carrigfadda church (1927) and Rosscarbery church (1929).
- 39 Vera Ryan, pers. comm. This is from a copy of notes taken by Vera when viewing the Watson's archive at the Crawford Art Gallery.
- 40 'And I say also unto thee, That thou art Peter, and upon this rock I will build my church; and the gates of hell shall not prevail against it. And I will give unto thee the keys of the kingdom of heaven' (Matthew 16:18-19).
- 41 See St Patrick's *Confessio*, available online at <https://confessio.ie> [accessed 30/09/2021].
- 42 Bieler, L. (ed.) 2004 (repr.). *The Patrician Texts in the Book of Armagh*. Dublin, p. 125.
- 43 See, for example, Gwynn, A. 1975-76. 'The problem of the Dicta Patricii'. *Seanchas Ardmbacha. Journal of the Armagh Diocesan Historical Society* 8(1), pp. 69-80.
- 44 McGee, C. M. 2020. 'Power, patronage and the production of Catholic material culture in nineteenth-century Ireland'. In R. Ingelbein and S. Galavan (eds) *Figures of Authority in Nineteenth-Century Ireland*. Liverpool, pp. 139-60, at p. 154.